

**The Sociological Consequences of the “Greater Serbia” Ideology: Genocide and Ethnic
Cleansing in Bosnia and Herzegovina**
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Abstract

The purpose of this article is an analysis of the sociological consequences of the Bosnian genocide and its impact on modern-day Bosnia and Herzegovina, by overviewing the “Greater Serbia” ideological project, which carried out crimes against humanity towards the local population of Srebrenica during the Genocide of July 1995. Arguing that the perpetrated acts by the Bosnian-Serb military forces were part of a deliberate and organised strategy aimed at creating an ethnically homogeneous Serbian state.

This article attempts to examine the role of Bosnian-Serb political, military and paramilitary forces, and it highlights the failure of the international community to prevent the genocide, with an emphasis on the Srebrenica case, due to its proclaimed status as a “safe area” by the United Nations in 1993. The study examines findings from international legal institutions, which confirm the existence of genocidal intent and responsibility by the Serbian political leadership.

Furthermore, the article dives into the demographic and sociological changes caused by the conflict and the perpetuated policies against the Bosnian population.

Census data from the Agency for Statistics of Bosnia and Herzegovina for 1991 and 2013 illustrate a significant decline in the Bosniak population in the entity of Republika Srpska, primarily due to forced displacement, and the emergence of mono-ethnic territorial divisions after the Dayton Agreement.

The article concludes, emphasising current issues that hinder stability and the identity of modern-day Bosnia and Herzegovina, through the legacy of genocide and the armed conflict of 1992-1995 and the ongoing reconciliation and political structure issues.

Introduction

The aggression perpetrated by the former Yugoslav and Serbian leadership against Bosnia and Herzegovina culminated in a systematic campaign of ethnic cleansing and genocide, aimed at establishing an ethnically homogeneous Greater Serbian state. These campaigns,

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including the Srebrenica genocide, should be analysed within the framework of relevant international conventions addressing the Holocaust, crimes against humanity, and genocide. These legal provisions emerged directly from the experiences and lessons following the Second World War.

An in-depth understanding of the Srebrenica Genocide calls for an analysis of its origins, underlying causes, consequences, and subsequent mechanisms. The genocide was perpetrated on July 11, 1995. Although Srebrenica had been designated a demilitarised United Nations “safe area” since 1993 and was ostensibly under international protection, the international community’s failure to respond adequately and assume responsibility—despite forewarnings—contributed to the mass killing of Bosniaks.

The events in Srebrenica show genocide is not spontaneous but a long, organised process, planned by perpetrators. Such processes are identifiable through clear doctrines, political leaders and military involvement, and actions that later become documented crimes. The Srebrenica Genocide was not isolated or accidental. It was a deliberate, organised act by a political system with a defined ideology and strategy.

Responsibility for the Srebrenica Genocide lay with specific individuals, political parties, political leaders, military and paramilitary forces, and, most significantly, the state structures of Serbia. Only the top political authorities could design such policies, use state institutions, and encourage hostility toward other groups. Attempting to change territory and population makeup, these leaders made key decisions that resulted in systematic violence against one ethnic group. Consequently, more than 100,000 people were killed, about 2.2 million were displaced, roughly 50,000 women were raped, over 1,000 religious sites were destroyed, and thousands were held in concentration camps.²

The Bosniak Genocide: Historical and Sociological Perspective

An important goal of the “Greater Serbian” ideology was the control of all the Bosnia and Herzegovina territory alongside the Drina river, being that the Serbs' main objective of the conflict (1992-1995) and afterwards was and still is to maintain a mono-ethnic population, exclusively Serb.

² Norman M. Naimark, *Genocide: A World History*, Oxford: University Press, 2017, p. 128; Joeden-Forgey, Elisa von, 'Gender and Genocide', and Cathie Carmichael, “[Genocide and Population Displacement in Post-Communist Eastern Europe.](#)” in Donald Bloxham, and A. Dirk Moses (eds), *The Oxford Handbook of Genocide Studies* (2010; online edn, Oxford Academic, 18 Sept. 2012), pp. 61-81 and pp. 509-529; Alexandra Stiglmayer, (Ed.). *Mass Rape: The War against Women in Bosnia-Herzegovina*. Lincoln, NB: University of Nebraska Press, 1995, p. 82-196.

Before the war in Bosnia and Herzegovina, these territories were inhabited by Bosniaks, Serbs, and Croats with varying percentages. To link and annex the Serbian ethnic component to the motherland and fulfil the ideological dream of “all Serbs in one country” (promoted by Slobodan Milosevic, then President of Serbia and President of the Federal Republic of Yugoslavia), Serbs initiated the ethnic cleansing of Bosniaks and the Srebrenica Genocide. To achieve this historical goal, forces from the Bosnian Serb Army, aided by allied militias supported by Belgrade, conducted widespread ethnic cleansing across about 3,600 towns and villages in Bosnia and Herzegovina. This campaign affected hundreds of thousands of Bosnian Muslims. The core aim was to forcibly remove Muslim populations—men, women, and children—from areas that Serb authorities claimed as their own territory.³

With the passage of Resolution 819 in 1993 by the Security Council, Srebrenica was declared a “safe-guarded zone”, which did not ward off the Serbs from commencing a military operation in the proclaimed “safe zone” of Srebrenica at the beginning of July, 1995. The operation received direct assistance from Serbian paramilitary groups, as well as volunteers from Greece and Russia. As noted by Weiss-Wendt (2010), of the roughly 10,000 Serb volunteers who participated in the conflict in Bosnia, about half had earlier experience in the Yugoslav People’s Army. Unsurprisingly, then, the military controlled most of the militias, with the rest run by the State Security Service.”⁴

The use of paramilitary forces was used efficiently to enable the Serbian political apparatus to deny direct responsibility for the use of military force against the territories of Bosnia and Herzegovina and for committing numerous crimes against humanity and the aforementioned genocide.

The UN proved to be incapable and powerless against the act of Serb militants. On July 11th, Serbian military forces occupied Srebrenica and initiated their genocidal campaign. In the span of one week, more than 8000 civilians were killed and hastily buried in mass graves, Bosniaks were beaten and publicly humiliated, children were killed in front of their parents, and women and girls alike were raped.⁵

³ Norman M. Naimark, *Genocide: A World History*, Oxford: University Press, 2017, pp. 126-127

⁴ Anton Weiss-Wendt, “[The State and Genocide.](#)” in Donald Bloxham, and A. Dirk Moses (eds), *The Oxford Handbook of Genocide Studies* (2010; online edn, Oxford Academic, 18 Sept. 2012), p. 95.

⁵ Elisa von Joeden-Forgey, “[Gender and Genocide.](#)” in Donald Bloxham, and A. Dirk Moses (eds), *The Oxford Handbook of Genocide Studies* (2010; online edn, Oxford Academic, 18 Sept. 2012), p. 69.

The Srebrenica genocide also led to the forced displacement of about 30,000 people, mostly women and children. During this period, Serbian troops repeatedly stopped buses and trucks carrying civilians to commit sexual violence against women, harass children, steal belongings, and separate young boys from their mothers to be killed. The bodies of these boys were later found in mass graves.⁶

The Serb approach was systematic. It started with surrounding Srebrenica to prepare for ethnic cleansing, then establishing a concentration camp. This operation cleared the way for the killing of local leaders, officers, and intellectuals. The atrocity included separating women, children, and elders from Bosniak men considered "combat ready" and thus potential ARBIIH recruits. Once these unarmed men were gathered, the final phase began: systematic executions and disposal of bodies in mass graves.⁷

Therefore, a carefully designed plan for genocide and ethnic cleansing clearly indicated that this was a conscious, deliberate and organised aim to radically change the demography of today's Bosnia and Herzegovina, which is clearly visible as a small percentage of Bosniaks are living in this region to this date. It is important to add that besides the ethnic cleansing and genocide, Serb political leaders and their military counterparts ensured also the destruction of cultural heritage, whereby many important historical, religious and cultural monuments were destroyed.

The international community, including the United Nations, failed to provide adequate protection for civilians in the "safe zone." They must bear accountability for not preventing the genocide. In this case, the United Nations violated several conventions: the Convention on the Prevention and Punishment of the Crime of Genocide (1948), the Geneva Conventions (1949), and their Additional Protocols (1977). Before the Serb military offensive, the mandate of the United Nations Protection Force (UNPROFOR) in the safe area was sharply limited, especially regarding air support. As a result, UNPROFOR left the civilian population to fend for itself. The force instead focused on the safety of its own personnel and the prolongation of so-called peace negotiations.

⁶ Campbell J. Kenneth. *Genocide and the Global Village*. New York: Palgrave, 2010, pp. 55-70; Norman M. Naimark, *Genocide: A World History*. Oxford: University Press, 2017, p. 129.

⁷ Adam Jones, *The Genocidal Mind: Sociological and Sexual Perspectives*. Lanham, MD: Rowman and Littlefield, 2006, p. 216.

It is hardly credible that the international community had no meaningful military and political capabilities to prevent the Srebrenica genocide and to act in time.

Why did the United Nations fail to call for resolute air power to protect civilians in Srebrenica? How was genocide carried out against Bosniaks with the Dutch Battalion present? Why did Dutch forces abandon critical checkpoints and transfer control to Serb militias?

The “Dutch UN peacekeepers could have protected the Bosnian Muslim population of the Srebrenica “safe area” against the killing spree that occurred.

The atrocities that have taken place in Srebrenica have shown that the acts of genocide were based on systematic planning and, as such, were justified by the Serbian political establishment. Therefore, “in 2007, in a case filed by Bosnia and Herzegovina against Serbia, the International Court of Justice said there had been a breach of the Genocide Convention because Serbia failed to intervene with its allies, the Bosnian Serbs, so as to prevent the Srebrenica massacre of July 1995.”⁸

The Hague sentences, including those concerning the Srebrenica Genocide, unambiguously affirm the occurrence of genocide.

intent, planning, preparation, organisation, and systematic execution of civilians, which was declared according to international law as genocide and crimes against humanity, confirming that such crimes were perpetuated and planned, which left very little space for taking up responsibility and feeling of guilt. It is not odd and uncommon to discover that genocide deniers are among those who directly committed it and live among people from whom those perpetrators of genocide belong.

Judgments issued in The Hague, along with extensive academic research on the Srebrenica genocide, clearly demonstrate that Serbian nationalist ideology, along with related political agendas and state policies, played a key role in enabling a genocide that was carefully planned, sustained, and systematically executed. Serbia tried to exploit the circumstances to seize territory from the sovereign state of Bosnia and Herzegovina and to eliminate Bosniaks as the country’s majority population.

When the war erupted, the Bosnian Serbs and the Croats armed themselves for a struggle to unite “their” respective population centres in Bosnia with their “homelands.”⁹

⁸ William A. Schabas, [“The Law and Genocide.”](#) in Donald Bloxham, and A. Dirk Moses (eds), *The Oxford Handbook of Genocide Studies* (2010; online edn, Oxford Academic, 18 Sept. 2012), p. 129.

⁹ Norman M. Naimark, [Genocide: A World History](#), Oxford: University Press, 2017, p. 126

The use of genocide was the ultimate tool to complete the destruction of a sovereign state and eradicate the Bosniak entity.

Decades after these events, the same Serbian nationalist ideology stands behind the denial of the Srebrenica Genocide. The exact same political establishment dated back to the '90s has managed so far to deny the admission of guilt of the Srebrenica Genocide, when questioned about the genocidal acts perpetrated by Serb forces, the Serbian politicians claim that the occurred events are a tragic crime in which both Serbs and Bosniaks share an equal sense of responsibility, and deny all evidence of a committed genocide, leading to the failed attempt to adopt the Resolution on Srebrenica Genocide by the Serbian Parliament, denying the long deserved apology to the Bosniak people and the victims.

There are, but only a few political leaders among the Serbs who publicly admitted that the Serbian entity has deliberately perpetrated the act of genocide in Bosnia and Herzegovina. This constitutes a systematic denial by the overall majority of the Serbian leadership and creates a precedent and a concrete danger for future conflicts where acts of genocide and similar atrocities may be committed once again, under the indifference of political leaders and the international audience, as we are witnessing now in other parts of the world such as the ongoing genocide of Gaza perpetrated by the State of Israel.¹⁰

More than thirty years have passed since the end of the Bosnian war, yet there is no unanimous consensus within the society of Bosnia and Herzegovina and its entities regarding the war, justice for its victims and the future of Bosnia and Herzegovina itself. The unresolved past even now haunts Bosnians today.

After the Dayton Peace Agreement the first elections of the Bosnian Presidential System made no restrictions on the nationalist parties that actively partake the war, therefore, prolonging the conflict through political means, as the Dayton Peace Agreement establishes preferences on ethno-nationalist division of power between the three main ethnical groups of Bosnia and Herzegovina, with regards to political, economic, ethnic, territorial and other divisions of the state and the society. Thus, it bolsters divisions between ethnicities within one federative state, giving no chance for reconciliation, peace, or a common future.¹¹

¹⁰ [Sentence of the UN Independent International Commission of Inquiry on the Occupied Palestinian Territory, United Nations Human Rights, 16th September 2025.](#)

¹¹ Muhidin Mulalic & Hasan Korkut. ["Implications of the Dayton Peace Agreement on Current Political Issues in Bosnia-Herzegovina."](#) *SDU Faculty of Arts and Sciences Journal of Social Sciences Special Issue on Balkans*, 2012, Vol. 27, pp. 107-117.

All prospects for transitional justice in Bosnia and Herzegovina are an inevitable process of peace-building, and have been seen as a mere “experiment” that will not bring any justice to any of the involved parties during the war. Hopes and expectations from the International Crime Tribunal for former Yugoslavia (ICTY) as a result of long trials, lack of transparency, questionable and meagre sentences for the surviving genocide perpetrators are lost, and there is complete apathy with regard to an institutional delivery of justice to the Bosnian people. All attempts from the International Community to serve justice, peace and reconciliation have been tampered with and seriously questioned by the reemergence of nationalist political parties that deny to this day any genocidal acts and threaten secession from Bosnia and Herzegovina.¹²

The question of the complete annihilation of Bosnia and Herzegovina's statehood identity has become an important focus of study among sociologists. It is remarkable that for some citizens, Bosnia and Herzegovina does not represent their country but the constituency of three distinct ethnicities within one State. The Bosnian nation-state is represented only through state symbols such as the passport, flag, and the institutions established by the Constitution. However, there is an overall sense of disaffection among the Bosnian population regarding their belonging to the State and its Society. It implies that Bosnia and Herzegovina, and its social construct, are living through a dire sociological dilemma.¹³

The terminology of justice, law and peace is used by Bosniaks, interconnecting and interrelating them to articulate the occurred genocide and the impossibility of a future without such terms.

Despite all the suffering, most Bosniaks firmly believe in a common shared future alongside Bosnian Serbs and Bosnian Croats inhabiting Bosnia and Herzegovina and the neighbouring states of Serbia and Croatia, but only if justice determined by the law is unanimously accepted by all parties.

However, Bosnian society has been struggling to achieve post-war justice and peace, due to a fragmentation into three parts of the truth, each truth changes and shifts the culprit and blames a different party involved in the war, denying their own involvement. This act is perpetrated by all ethnic groups belonging to Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bosniaks, Croats and

¹² [U.S. Embassy statement on Milorad Dodik's Secessionist threats, former President of Republika Srpska.](#)

¹³ Elvis Fejzic, Research article [“Contemporary politics in Bosnia and Herzegovina: historical determinants and political experiences”](#), University of Sarajevo 2023, pp. 57-58

Serbs alike.

This dilemma keeps the nation-state of Bosnia and Herzegovina in endless stagnation, preventing any hope for a brighter future from being built on the shoulders of its people. Due to the complexity of these traits and their political implications, sociologists have failed to explore them in depth.

Ethnic Cleansing and Genocide's Impact on Demography

The Genocide and ethnic cleansing in Bosnia and Herzegovina, with an emphasis on the Eastern part bordering the Drina River, were diligently orchestrated by the Serb leadership. This vile act was based on the byproduct of Serbian radical hegemonic ideology that began to spread during the 1990s. The idea of a restoration of a Greater Serbia was reinforced not only by the political elites, but also by intellectuals and the Orthodox clergy, which played a major role in shaping the ideological vision of a restored Serbian state, by carrying out ethnic cleansing and genocide, which were planned and deliberately approved by politicians, bureaucrats and high-ranking military officials against the Bosniak people.¹⁴

During the self-proclaimed “16th assembly of the Serb People” that was held on May 12th, 1992, in Banja Luka, ethnic cleansing was officially adopted as a political objective by the Serbs. In this context, it is important to highlight the adoption of the document known as the “Six Strategic Goals of the Serbian People”(Hikmet Karcic, 2022).

The main objective was the separation of the ethnic Serb majority of eastern Bosnia and Herzegovina from the Bosniak and Croat ethnic groups.

The “Six Strategic Goals of the Serbian People” included the following: 1) the establishment of state borders as to separate the ethnic Serbs from Croats and Bosniaks; 2) the creation of a corridor that would connect Semberija and Krajina regions; 3) the complete assimilation and control of the Drina river valley by the Serbian people, therefore eliminating the natural border between Serbia and Bosnia and Hercegovina; 4) the establishment of a new border between the rivers of Una and Neretva; 5) the partition and the gentrification of the city of Sarajevo into distinct Serbian and Muslim neighborhoods and the establishment of effective

¹⁴ Norman M. Naimark, *Genocide: A World History*, Oxford: University Press, 2017

separate state authorities in both areas; 6) acquire a foothold in the Adriatic sea for Republika Srpska.¹⁵

As a result of the successful ethnic cleansing campaign, the Republika Srpska emerged as one of the three recognised administrative units within Bosnia and Herzegovina.

The current territories of the entity are Bosnian-Serbian by majority (see table 1)

Table 1: Republika Srpska territories demographic changes, 1991 and 2013 comparison

Census 1991			Census 2013		
Bosniaks:	441.077	28,0%	Bosniaks:	171.839	14,0%
Croats:	144.129	9,2%	Croats:	29.645	2,4%
Serbs:	872.610	55,5%	Serbs:	1.001.299	81,5%
Others:	114.799	7,3%	Others:	25.640	2,1%
Σ :	1.572.615		Σ :	1.228.423	

¹⁵ Hikmet Karcic, [Torture, Humiliate, Kill: Inside the Bosnian Serb Camp System, 2022](#), University of Michigan Press, pp. 27-28

	1991	2013
Name	-	Republika Srpska
Total population	1.572.615	1.228.423
Bosniaks	441.077 (28,0 %)	171.839 (14,0 %)
Croats	144.129 (9,2 %)	29.645 (2,4 %)
Serbs	872.610 (55,5 %)	1.001.299 (81,5 %)
Others	114.799 (7,3 %)	25.640 (2,1 %)
Površina ukupno	24.641,72 km ²	24.641,72 km ²

Source: Agency for Statistics of Bosnia and Herzegovina

<http://www.statistika.ba>

As shown in Table 2, Bosnia and Herzegovina's population in 2013 stood at 3.531.159 (1.086.733 Serbs, 544.780 Croats, and 1.769.592 Bosniaks), representing a decline of 845.874 people from the 1991 census—an overall decrease of roughly 19.3%. Unlike in previous decades, the 2013 census clearly shows a significant population decline. Among several contributing factors, a primary cause of this decline was the 1992–1995 war, during which 95.940 individuals lost their lives, around two million were displaced internally or externally, and approximately 1.2 million were forced to emigrate abroad.¹⁶

Table 2: Population change of Bosnia and Herzegovina from 1991 to 2013

	1991	2013
Name	Republic of Bosnia und Herzegovina	Bosnia und Herzegovina
Total population	4.377.033	3.531.159
Bosniaks	1.902.956 (43,5 %)	1.769.592 (50,1 %)
Croats	760.852 (17,4 %)	544.780 (15,4 %)
Serbs	1.366.104 (31,2 %)	1.086.733 (30,8 %)
Others	347.121 (7,9 %)	130.054 (3,7 %)
Površina ukupno	51.222,84 km ²	51.222,84 km ²

Source: Agency for Statistics of Bosnia and Herzegovina

<http://www.statistika.ba>

Table 3 further highlights a pronounced mono-ethnic population distribution within both entities of Bosnia and Herzegovina. In the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bosniaks make up 70.4% of the population, followed by Croats at 22.44%, while Serbs account for just 2.55%. Conversely, Republika Srpska is predominantly Serb, with 81.51% of its population, alongside 13.98% Bosniaks and only 2.41% Croats. The District of Brcko remarks the only exception with its homogeneous population represented by all three main ethnicities (42.4% Bosniaks, followed by 34.6% Serbs and 20.7% Croats).

¹⁶ Mirko Pejanovic, [Ethnic structure changes in BiH municipalities according to the 2013 census](#), in Cvitkovic Ivan (Ed.). *Demografske i Etnicke promjene u Bosni I Hercegovini*. Sarajevo: ANUBiH, 2017, pp. 70-74

Table 3: Population distribution between the entities of BiH

	1991	2013
Name	-	Federation of Bosnia und Herzegovina
Total population	2.711.291	2.219.220
Bosniaks	1.419.262 (52,3 %)	1.562.372 (70,4 %)
Croats	593.471 (21,9 %)	497.883 (22,4 %)
Serbs	475.866 (17,6 %)	56.550 (2,5 %)
Others	222.692 (8,2 %)	102.415 (4,6 %)
Površina ukupno	26.087,53 km ²	26.087,53 km ²

	1991	2013
Name	-	Republika Srpska
Total population	1.572.615	1.228.423
Bosniaks	441.077 (28,0 %)	171.839 (14,0 %)
Croats	144.129 (9,2 %)	29.645 (2,4 %)
Serbs	872.610 (55,5 %)	1.001.299 (81,5 %)
Others	114.799 (7,3 %)	25.640 (2,1 %)
Površina ukupno	24.641,72 km ²	24.641,72 km ²

	1991	2013
Name	Brčko	Brčko
Total population	87.627	83.516
Bosniaks	38.617 (44,1 %)	35.381 (42,4 %)
Croats	22.252 (25,4 %)	17.252 (20,7 %)
Serbs	18.128 (20,7 %)	28.884 (34,6 %)
Others	8.630 (9,8 %)	1.999 (2,4 %)
Površina ukupno	493,60 km ²	493,60 km ²

Source: Agency for Statistics of Bosnia and Herzegovina

<http://www.statistika.ba>

Table 4: Bosniak population decrease in Republika Srpska entity (from 1991 to 2013)

Town	Population Decrease (with more than four thousand)
Zvornik	- 28.247
Doboj	- 25.842
Banja Luka	-20.907
Prijedor	- 20.317
Bosanska Krupa	- 19.526
Foča	- 19.520
Bijeljina	- 17.139

Vlasenica	- 14.964
Srebrenica	- 14.163
Bratunac	- 13.732
Višegrad	- 12.428
Rogatica	- 12.092
Lopare	- 10.619
Gradiška	- 8.271
Ugljevik	- 8.056
Novi Grad	- 7.601
Modriča	- 7.274
Kotor-Varoš	- 5.856
Teslić	- 5.618
Derventa	- 5.191
Trebinje	- 4.576

Source: Agency for Statistics of Bosnia and Herzegovina

<http://www.statistika.ba>

Table 5: Bosniaks from majority to minority in RS towns (1991 to 2013)

Town	Percentage 1991	Percentage 2013
Zvornik	59,16%	33,76%
Bratunac	64,32%	38,38%
Foča	50,98 %	6,98 %
Vlasenica	55,53 %	32,75 %
Rogatica	59,36 %	10,37 %
Višegrad	63,09 %	9,59 %
Srebrenica	75,50%	54,68%

Source: Agency for Statistics of Bosnia and Herzegovina
<http://www.statistika.ba>

Tables 4 and 5 list towns and cities that suffered significant losses of Bosniak inhabitants; the percentage of Bosniaks in cities such as Zvornik, Bratunac, Foča, Vlasenica, Rogatica, Višegrad, and Srebrenica has decreased significantly.

It clearly indicates demographic changes caused by ethnic cleansing, genocide and war perpetrated by the modern-day entity Republika Srpska.

Conclusion

The campaign of ethnic cleansing and genocide that occurred in Bosnia and Herzegovina, with a remark on the Srebrenica Genocide, should not be assumed as exclusively related to wartime and as mere consequences of an armed conflict.

As this article explains, these acts represented a deliberate, ideologically motivated plan to change the state's demographic and sociological composition. The use of systematic violence against the population through coordinated military operations, with the participation of professional and paramilitary troops, and the dramatic demographic changes confirm that genocide was used as the primary tool for reshaping the territory of Bosnia and Herzegovina. The significant population decline between 1991 and 2013, as illustrated by the Agency for Statistics of Bosnia and Herzegovina, is unequivocal. Alongside the formation of predominantly mono-ethnic entities (Bosniak, Croat and Serb), it demonstrates the long-term effectiveness of ethnic cleansing policies adopted to fulfill the Greater Serbia ideological objectives: the significant removal of Bosniak population from regions along the Drina River is the primary example of the implementation of a premeditated strategic vision, articulated in the nationalist document named "The Six Strategic Goals". The consequences of the demographic changes caused by the genocide are permanently embedded in the territorial and social construct of modern-day Bosnia and Herzegovina.

It is through the creation of the modern nation-state of Bosnia and Herzegovina that the sociological aspects of the aforementioned events have proven profound and relevant to this day.

The post-war state, shaped by the Dayton agreement, has entrenched ethnic divisions to the extent that the government and social structure of Bosnia and Herzegovina is incapable of acting as a unified polity, instead being driven by a fragmented collection of rivalling ethno-national entities. Furthermore, the persistence of exclusive narratives by each ethnic group, the common and rampant denial of genocide in the entity of Republika Srpska and the

absence of a shared historical background as one nation, resulted in a Bosnian society characterised by distrust, disaffection and political inertia towards the state of Bosnia and Herzegovina. To this day, the concept of a shared and cohesive Bosnian identity among its major ethnic components is heavily contested and undermined by its legacy of conflicts and violence and the current political situation.

Furthermore, the limited effectiveness of international tribunals, alongside the domestic rehabilitation of nationalist political parties, has fostered a pervasive sense of impunity among the local population.

This directly undermines all efforts of reconciliation and perpetuates the ideological schemes that enabled the war and its atrocities in the first place.

The current genocide denial campaign by Bosnian-Serb politicians, spearheaded by former President of Republika Srpska Milorad Dodik, is a continuation of the logic behind the “Greater Serbia” ideological plan, through political means rather than conventional warfare.¹⁷ Without concrete action by competent political bodies, both domestic and international, the prospects of stability and peace within the multi-ethnic nation-state will remain distant and unattainable.

¹⁷ Stefano Fella, [Bosnia and Herzegovina: secessionism in the Republika Srpska](#), House of Commons Library, UK Parliament, 2025, pp. 10; 13; 18

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